

SILICOSIS - OCCUPATIONAL DISEASE IN DENTAL TECHNICIAN**SILIKOZA - PROFESIONALNO OBOLJENJE KOD ZUBNOG TEHNIČARA**

Ivan Mikov^{1,2}, Siniša Đekić³, Ivan Turkalj^{1,2}, Mirjana Glavaški-Kraljević^{2,4}

¹ Clinical Center of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia

² University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad, Serbia

³ Institute of Public Health Novi Sad, Serbia

⁴ Institute of Occupational Health Novi Sad, Serbia

SUMMARY

Background: Silicosis is a chronic and progressive nodular pulmonary fibrosis caused by inhalation of inorganic dust quartz. The aim of the paper was to present occupational of silicosis in dental technician.

Case Report: A case of pulmonary silicosis in dental technician, recognized as occupational disease was analyzed. The patient has worked 38 years at the workplace dental technician, making denture with grindstone and was exposed to quartz dust, well above the maximal allowable concentration (64.8 or 102.5 mg/m³). His medical history revealed weakness, fatigue on light physical load and productive cough. He was hospitalized due to spontaneous pneumothorax, when on the chest X-ray diffuse small opacities, predominantly in the upper third of the lung fields, i.e. pneumoconiotic changes r/r, 1/2 (according to The International Labor Organization international radiographic classification of pneumoconiosis), as well as extended hilum and emphysema were found. Body plethysmography showed heavy mixed disorder of ventilation.

Conclusion. The patient completely loses the work ability due to silica dust exposure at workplace. Implementation of all preventive measures, including preventive medical surveillance of dental technicians in occupational health services could contribute to detection of the disease in the early stage and maintain work ability.

Keywords: Silicosis, occupational disease, workplace, dental technician, dentistry

SAŽETAK

UVOD: Silikoza je plućna fibroza nodularnog tipa koju izaziva udisanje neorganske prašine kvarca, a koja je po svom toku hronična i progredijentna. Cilj rada je bio prikaz profesionalne silikoze kod zubnog tehničara.

PRIKAZ SLUČAJA: Analiziran je slučaj silikoze pluća kod zubnog tehničara kod koga je priznato profesionalno oboljenje. Pacijent je 38 godina radio na radnom mestu zubnog tehničara, na izradi proteza brusnim kamenom i bio izložen kvarcnoj prašini znatno iznad maksimalno dozvoljenih koncentracija (64,8 odnosno 102,5 mg/m³). Anamneza je ukazala na slabost, zamaranje pri najmanjem fizičkom naprezanju i produktivan kašalj. Hospitalizovan je zbog spontanog pneumotoraksa, kada su na radiogramu pluća nađene difuzne sitnomrljaste promene, pretežno u gornjim trećinama plućnih polja koje odgovaraju pneumokoniotičnim promenama r/r, 1/2 (prema internacionalnoj radiološkoj klasifikaciji pneumokonioza Međunarodne organizacije rada), kao i prošireni hilusi i emfizem. Telesnom pletizmografijom nađen je težak mešoviti poremećaj ventilacije.

ZAKLJUČAK: Pacijent je potpuno izgubio radnu sposobnost zbog izloženosti silikogenoj prašini na radnom mestu. Sprovođenje svih preventivnih mera, uključujući preventivne medicinske preglede zubnih tehničara u službama medicine rada doprinelo bi otkrivanju bolesti u početnom stadijumu i očuvanju radne sposobnosti.

Ključne reči: Silkoza, profesionalno oboljenje, radno mesto, zubni tehničar, stomatologija

INTRODUCTION

Pneumoconioses are occupational lung diseases caused by inhalation and accumulation of mineral dust in lungs. Silicosis is fibrotic pneumoconiosis, a chronic and progressive nodular pulmonary fibrosis result from the inhalation of inorganic dust quartz (1, 2).

The International Labor Organization (ILO) plays significant role in prevention of pneumoconiosis. ILO and World Health Organization have initiated Global program of the elimination of silicosis (3). Also, ILO continuously publishes and distributes all over the world standards of its International classification of radiographs of pneumoconiosis including guidelines for the use (4, 5). Recently, international group of experts has developed International classification of high-resolution computed tomography for occupational respiratory diseases (6).

Identification of workers at risk, implementation of work safety measures and health surveillance by occupational health services are the most important preventive measures in reducing of pneumoconiosis (7).

The aim of the paper was to present occupational silicosis in dental technician.

CASE REPORT

The patient has worked 38 years at the workplace dental technician, making denture with grindstone and was exposed to quartz dust, well above the maximal allowable concentration (MAC) 64.8 or 102.5 mg/m³. He performed his tasks in a small workroom that had no mechanism for control of air pollution. He wore disposable medical examination gloves as personal protective device.

His medical history revealed weakness, fatigue on light physical load and productive cough. He had lost 10 kilograms of the body weight.

He was hospitalized due to spontaneous pneumothorax, when on the chest X-ray diffuse small opacities, predominantly in the upper

third of the lung fields, i.e. pneumoconiotic changes r/r, 1/2, according to the ILO international radiographic classification of pneumoconiosis, as well as extended hilum and emphysema (hi, em) were found (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. RTG of patient.

Body plethysmography showed heavy mixed disorder of ventilation.

Occupational silicosis was confirmed in the presented dental technician, according to the Rulebook on determining occupational diseases, at the Institute of Occupational Health Novi Sad (8).

The patient completely loses the work ability. Afterwards he got disability retirement.

DISCUSSION

A case of pulmonary silicosis in dental laboratory technician, recognized as occupational disease was analyzed.

In our region according to the register of occupational diseases in Vojvodina at the Institute of Occupational Health in Novi Sad, pulmonary silicosis is the most frequent

pneumoconiosis. However, cases of silicosis were only registered in the metal and construction industry (7).

There are numerous chemical hazards in prosthesis production: solvents, mineral acids, gases and vapors released during polymerization, as well as dust coming from plaster, metal alloys, ceramics and acrylic resins (9). Also, dental professionals may be at increased risk of developing occupational allergic diseases especially to methacrylate that can permeate protective disposable gloves (10). The measurements in a dental laboratory, carried out in Belgrade by the Institute of Occupational Health, recorded the levels of respirable dust containing 10% silica to exceed MAC by 3.6 times during sandblasting of metal and by 2.6 times during ceramics grinding (9).

Exposure to dust with high silica concentrations presents a risk of developing pneumoconiosis and it was found at the presented case.

Local ventilation systems must be properly constructed in dental laboratories to prevent respiratory exposure to airborne

contaminants. Adequate general ventilation and enclosure systems are also important (9).

In order to increase the efficiency of protecting workers' health, it is important to maintain workplace health management in addition to workplace dust exposure management. Workplace health management involves ongoing worker health monitoring to recognize abnormalities early on so as to initiate appropriate measures to prevent disease occurrence and to provide the necessary care to prevent disease progression (11).

CONCLUSION

The patient completely loses the work ability due to airborne exposure to high concentrations of silica dust at dental technician workplace. Besides of air pollution control in working environment, implementation of other preventive measures, including preventive medical surveillance of dental technicians in occupational health services could contribute to the detection of the disease in the early stage and maintain work ability.

REFERENCES

1. Karkhanis VS, Joshi JM. Pneumoconioses. *Indian J Chest Dis Allied Sci* 2013;55:25-34.
2. Leung CC, Yu ITS, Chen W. Silicosis. *Lancet* 2012;379:2008-18.
3. ILO/WHO Working group. ILO/WHO Global Program of Elimination Silicosis. In: *The Proceedings of 10th International Conference of Occupational Respiratory Diseases*. Beijing (China) 2005, Apr 19-22. Beijing: ILO, 2005:13-8.
4. International Labor Office (ILO). *Guidelines for the Use of ILO International classification of radiographs of pneumoconiosis*. Occupational safety and health services, No. 22 (Rev. 2011). Geneva: ILO, 2011.
5. Mikov I, Glavaski M, Crepulja J. Importance of international classification of radiographs in recognition of pneumoconiosis as occupational disease. *Pneumon* 2008;45:89-93.
6. Suganuma N, Kusaka Y, Hering KG, Vehmas T, Kraus T, Arakawa T, et al. Reliability of the proposed international classification of high-resolution computed tomography for occupational and environmental diseases. *J Occup Health* 2009;51:210-22.
7. Pericević-Medic S, Mikov I, Milicevic B, Glavaski-Kraljevic M, Crepulja J, Spanović M. Pneumoconioses in Autonomous Province of Vojvodina in the period 2000-2009. *Zdravstvena Zaštita* 2011;6:55-63.
8. The rulebook on determining occupational diseases. Official Decree, Republic of Serbia, Number 105/2003.
9. Torbica N, Krstev S. World at work: Dental laboratory technicians. *Occup Environ Med* 2006;63:145-8.
10. Mikov I, Turkalj I, Jovanović M. Occupational contact allergic dermatitis in dentistry. *Vojnosanitet Pregl* 2011;68(6):523-5.
11. Awn N, Imanaka M, Suganuma N. Japanese workplace health management in pneumoconiosis prevention. *J Occop Health* 2017;59:91-103.

KONFLIKT INTERESA - Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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Corresponding author:

Prof. dr Ivan Mikov

Clinical Center of Vojvodina,

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine

Hajduk Veljkova 1, Novi Sad, Serbia

E-mail: ivan.mikov@mf.uns.ac.rs

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